

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

GLOBAL WARMING AND ITS PREDICTION

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Abstract

In the article, the prediction of global warming based on modern satellite data is defined by years. Climate models take into account the influence of changes in solar activity, as well as the influence of volcanic activity. If we take into account the total area of the planet, the change in the angle of the surface to the sun's rays, and the fact that half of the Earth is in shadow, the actual energy received on average per year outside the atmosphere decreases. Despite the fact that there are many characteristics of the weather (wind, precipitation, etc.), it is more appropriate to conduct research on the temperature change of the air in the first approximation of the climate.

Keywords: Climate, prediction, temperature change, available energy, fixed, satellite data, atmospheric convection, greenhouse.

Our planet earth receives almost all its heat from the sun. According to modern satellite data, every square meter of area located outside the atmosphere and placed at right angles to the sun's rays receive 1365 watts of solar radiation energy. This sun is "fixed". For skeptics, it should be noted that none of them are constant and vary within $\pm 3\%$ depending on the activity of the sun, the season the method of measurement and calculation [1]. Climate models take into account the influence of changes in solar activity, as well as the influence of volcanic activity [2].

If we take into account the total area of the planet, the change in the angle of the surface to the sun's rays, and the fact that half of the Earth is in shadow, the actual energy received on average per year outside the atmosphere decreases (to 340 watts per square meter). When it reaches the earth, part of this energy is reflected from the clouds, the surface of the continents,

and the oceans, the atmosphere itself, is absorbed and released again. As a result, only 250 Watt m^{-2} of energy is available to drive the climate heat engine. This quantity is known with less accuracy ($\pm 10\%$) than the solar constant. In comparison, the effect of heat from deep within the planet is small, amounting to only 0.03 Watt m^{-2} , or about 0.01% of the available energy. The direct effect of human-generated heat is about the same magnitude, about 0.04 Watt m^{-2} [3]. From a practical point of view, climate is perceived by humans and by the bulk of the biosphere as the average regime of air near the Earth's surface, where we live and operate. Despite the fact that there are many characteristics of the weather (wind, precipitation, etc.), it is more appropriate to conduct research on the temperature change of the air in the first approximation of the climate.

Figure 1. Distribution of temperature changes by years.

Atmospheric convection helps combat global warming by moving water vapor above the bulk of the atmosphere, where it releases heat during condensation, thereby radiating heat more efficiently to the surrounding space. Atmospheric convection helps combat global warming by moving water vapor above the bulk of the atmosphere, where it releases heat during condensation, thereby radiating heat more efficiently to the surrounding space.

Currently, volcanic activity is considered the main factor that can change the value of the solar heat balance. Geochemical studies of glaciers and other sediments make it possible to revise the activity of volcanoes in the historical period quite well and to compare it with temperature changes [4]. Indeed, many historical coolings can be explained, if not entirely, by bursts of activity and its "unsuccessful" geographical and seasonal configuration, where again the dynamics of the atmosphere manifests itself: not all volcanoes affect the climate in the same way [5]. A number of recently published works show that there are changes in the dynamics of convective processes, as they affect the amount, organization, reflectivity and radiation of heat from the surface of cloudiness, and also affect the

heat balance and temperature of the planet significantly [6]. Heat exchange with the ocean directly changes the temperature—the amplitudes of such changes are very small. Unfortunately, the dynamics of the interaction between the atmosphere and the ocean is still not sufficiently studied due to the resonance and nonlinearity of the relationship [7]. But whatever the changes in dynamics and thermodynamics, it is a fact that the temperature has changed by more than 0.5°C (figure 1).

From the middle of the 19th century, unusual things happen. The two processes - an unprecedented increase in temperature of more than 1°C in 100 years and a simultaneous increase in carbon dioxide (CO_2) of more than 40% - are going in parallel. In addition, a strong increase in the concentration of methane, nitrogen oxides and other "greenhouse" gases. It is not difficult to prove that the reason for the increase in CO_2 concentration is the burning of residual slopes. For this, coal, oil, gas, etc. there is no need to study the statistics of production and use, but these statistics are sufficiently known, it is enough to study the change of the isotopic composition of carbon. The composition of CO_2 and oxygen in the atmosphere is given in figure 2.

Figure 2. Dynamics of CO_2 and oxygen content in the atmosphere

Three isotopes of carbon are found in nature in various compounds, minerals, air and ocean water. The most abundant (about 98% of the total amount of this element is stable isotope, ^{12}C , consists of 6 protons and 6 neutrons. The seven-neutron stable isotope ^{13}C is about 1%. There is also a small admixture of the long-lived radioactive isotope ^{14}C with eight neutrons, which is formed from atmospheric nitrogen as a result of exposure to cosmic radiation in the air and oceanic

upper crust. Accurate measurements of isotope ratios, such as the $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio in the mass of carbon dioxide and methane in the air, reveal the sources of observed changes in the concentrations of these greenhouse gases. Plants preferentially absorb ^{12}C . Therefore, the produced fuels are enriched in this isotope. Figure 3 shows the prediction and experimental results with different combinations of radiation effects.

Figure 3. Temperature anomalies and modeling results calculated on the basis of historical climate changes.

The consequences of climate change

But it's not just about rising temperatures. Climate change leads to many unpredictable consequences in a variety of areas, including:

- Climate change is intensifying the water cycle, resulting in heavy rainfall and associated flooding in some regions and extreme droughts in others.
- Climate change affects precipitation patterns. In high latitudes, the probability of precipitation increases, while in most of the subtropics it decreases.
- Coastal areas will continue to experience rising sea levels in the 21st century, which in turn will contribute to more frequent and severe flooding in low-lying areas and soil erosion. Extreme changes in sea level, which used to occur once every 100 years, will occur annually towards the end of this century.
- Further warming will increase the melting of permafrost, loss of snow cover and shrinking glaciers in the Arctic.
- Changes in the state of the world's oceans will cause more frequent warm currents, which will affect the ecosystem of the ocean and the people who live off fishing.
- Particular aspects of climate change may affect urban residents, who will experience a warming climate, as well as flooding due to heavy rainfall and rising sea levels in coastal regions.

Suggestions

The main goal is to reduce the use of fossil fuels such as oil, carbon and gas and replace them with renewable and clean energy sources, while increasing energy efficiency.

"By the end of the next decade, we must almost halve our CO₂ emissions (by 45%)

The path to this goal involves daily steps, such as cutting back on car travel and reducing air travel, switching to a green energy provider, and some changes in diet and food choices.

It seems that the problem of global warming will not disappear if a few conscientious individuals start buying ecological products or switch to a bicycle.

However, many experts agree that such decisions are important - they affect the behavior of our acquaintances, forcing them to also change their lifestyle sooner or later.

Other changes involve major systemic transformations, such as upgrading energy and food industry subsidies that still encourage the use of fossil fuels.

As well as the introduction of new rules and initiatives for such industries as agriculture, forestry and waste disposal.

References

1. Soon W., Connolly R., C & Connolly M. (2015) Re-evaluating the role of solar variability on Northern Hemisphere temperature trends since the 19th century. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 150/409-452/ doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2015.08.001.
2. Canty T., Mascioli N.R., Smarte M.D., & Salawitch R.J. (2013). An empirical model of global climate---Part I: A critical evaluation of volcanic cooling. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 13(8), 3997-4031. doi.org/10.5194/acp-13-3997-2013.
3. "Key World Energy Statistics 2019" International Energy Agency. 26 September 2019. Pp. 6, 36. Retrieved 7 January 2020.
4. Robock, A. (2000), Volcanic eruptions and climate, *Rev. Geophys.*, 38, 191-219.
5. Bronnimann S., Franke J., Nussbaumer S.U. et al. Last phase of the Little Ice Age forced by volcanic eruption. *Nat. Geosci.* 12, 650-656 (2019) doi:10.1038/s41561-019-0402-y
6. Schneider T., Kaul C.M., & Pressel K.G. (2019). Possible climate transitions from breakup of stratocumulus decks under greenhouse warming. *Nature Geoscience*, 12(3), 163-167. doi.org/10.1038/s41561-019-0310-1.
7. Shepherd T.G. (2014) Atmospheric circulation as a source of uncertainty in climate change projections. *Nature Geosciences*, doi.org/10.1038/NGEO2253 doi.org/10.1038/NGEO2398.